

TYOLOGY OF WOMEN RELEASED FROM PENAL JURISDICTION

Nasirov Izzatilla Sunnat o'g'li

Teacher of the Department of "Penalty Execution Activities" of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7809615>

Abstract. In this scientific article, the author has studied the typology of women who have committed crimes and who have been released from punishment, and reveals the reasons and methods of classifying them into types.

Key words: woman, behavior, ethics, classification, description, separation, social, psychological, typology, crime, recidivism.

It is stipulated by normative and legal documents that every prisoner brought to the penal institution to serve his sentence should be kept in the detention center for 15 days ¹. During this time, the colony staff should study the prisoners, create a psychological portrait and divide them into types.

If we pay attention to the typology of women in penal institutions, typology means classification and separation according to their main characteristics ². Typology is the identification of similar types according to a set of internal characteristics of phenomena or objects, based on the concept of type or type as a unique ideal model of historically developing objects.

Cases of prosecution for crimes committed by women are also on the rise. Particularly, in 2018, criminal punishment was applied to 4,374 women, of which: fine - 1 095 persons, deprivation of certain rights - 8 persons, compulsory public works - 76 persons, correctional works - 902 persons, restriction of liberty - 1,219 persons, deprivation of liberty - 566 persons, conditional sentence - 508 persons, a total of 3,112 women in 2019, of which: fine - 716 persons, deprivation of certain rights - 5 persons, compulsory community service - 50 people, correctional works - 524 people, o restriction of freedom - 1010 people, o deprivation of freedom " - 435 people, conditional sentence - 372 people, a total of 3,027 women in 2020, of which: fine - 506 people, deprivation of certain rights - 6 people, compulsory community service - 52 people, correctional work - 579 people , restriction of freedom - 1207 people, deprivation of freedom - 427 people, conditional sentence - 250 people, a total of 5,040 women in 2021, of which: fine - 862 people, deprivation of certain rights - 5 people, compulsory community service - 79 people, correctional works - 940 people, restriction of freedom - 2,041 people, deprivation of freedom - 806 people, conditional sentence - 307 people, a total of 6,497 women in 2022, of which: fine - 1,146 people, deprivation of certain rights - 12 people,

¹ Order " On approving the rules of the internal procedure of the institutions of the deprivation of liberty of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan" <https://lex.uz/docs/2216121> // (time of reference to the electronic database: 03.04.2023).

² Typology // <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D0%A2%D0%B8%D0%BF%D0%BE%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B3%D0%B8%D1%8F> // (time of database access: 02/02/2023).

compulsory public works - 94 people, correctional works - 1,246 people, restriction of liberty - 2,439 persons, deprivation of liberty - 1,241 persons, conditional sentence - 319 persons³.

The theoretical foundation of the typology of women has been studied by many scientists. V.G. Belinsky was one of the first to divide women into active and passive types⁴. In opinion of some scientists, law enforcement bodies depend on the development of a typology of the criminal in order to prevent crime at the individual level. It was emphasized that this typology forms the basis of the method of forecasting individual behavior and applying measures of differentiated and individualized preventive legal influence⁵.

In opinion of criminologist K.E. Igoshev, a specific model of a person is created by dividing the criminal into types, and the determination of conformity to this model should indicate that he belongs to a certain type of person⁶.

In the studies of criminological scientists V.D. Pakhomov and I.V. Korzun, more attention was paid to the description of certain reasons that motivate deviant behavior in recent times⁷. Professor Q.R. Abdurasulova said that the typology of female convicts is different, that is, according to other signs and criteria, signs of participation in socio-psychological and criminal activities of criminal and legal significance, and the object of criminal aggression. can⁸

In O.E. Nazareva's opinion, the personality of the prisoner can be defined as a certain model, a socio-psychological type with specific characteristics. It is characterized by antisocial views, a negative attitude to moral values, and choosing a socially dangerous way to satisfy one's needs or not showing the necessary activity in preventing a negative outcome.^{9 10} expressed their opinions.

In our opinion, the typology of the criminal personality is a method of systematic modeling of the mechanism of crime prevention, taking into account the unique assessment of the criminal personality, seeing the infinite variety of individual characteristics of individuals, certain socially generalized images or types.

Typology has an objective criterion and summarizes the set of characteristics characteristic of all or certain groups, while classification has a somewhat subjective character, since it assigns criminals to arbitrarily selected characteristics. It divides into groups. The relationship between the typology of the criminal person, his classification and the person who committed the crime can be expressed as a unit of generality (typology), specificity (classification) and uniqueness (specific person).

³ <https://stat.sud.uz/file/2023/09.02/%D1%81%D0%B0%D0%B9%D1%82%20%D0%B6%D0%B8%D0%BD%D0%BE%D1%8F%D1%82%202022%20%D0%B9%D0%B8%D0%BB%2012%20%D0%BE%D0%B9.pdf> (time of database access: 04/06/2023).

⁴ Friday G. K., Erbulatova I. K. GRNTI 17.82. 90 <https://doi.org/10.52081/bkaku.2022.v63.i4.170> Typology of female images and produced "zuleykha otkryvaet glaz" g. yakhinoy //Korkyt Ata atyndagy Kyzylorda University. - S. 117. Belinsky, V.G. Izbrannye stati // Saratov: Privoljskoe, 1974. - 208 str.

⁵ Criminology. - St. Petersburg : Lan, 1998.-S.135.

⁶ I Goshev K.E. Typology lichnosti p restupn i ka i motivation prestup n ogo behavior Gorky. 1974.-S. 5 5.

⁷ P a hom o v V. _ D., Korzun I.V. _ Osobennosti prophylactic Jensk o.y _ adultery o r ganami vnutrennix Del // Sovremennaya prestupnost: newer Isledovaniya. - M., 1993. - S. 108-109.

⁸ Abdurasulova Q. _ R. _ " Women's crime and problems of their prevention " . Study guide / Responsible editor: yu.fd.prof. MHRustamboev. - T.: TDYI publishing house, 2009. - 31 pages.

⁹ See : Nazareva O.E. Osobennosti lichnosti ouzdenno, otbyvayushchego nakazanie bez isozlyatsii ot obshchestva // Ugolovno-ispolnitelnoe pravo. 2007. No. 1. 80 p.

¹⁰ See : Criminology: uchebnik / pod ed. V.N. Burlakova, NM Kropacheva. SPb., 2002. 151-152 p.

According to the criminologist G.A. Avanesov, it is possible to talk about different directions of studying the personality of the criminal on the basis of typology¹¹. G.G.Zuykov said that a crime committed in a certain way allows to learn not only the "origin" of the criminal, his individual method of committing the crime, but also shows the type of the criminal's personality¹².

Professor

Q.R. Abdurasulova is related to women by analyzing the surrounding events, the following micro split into environments: -educational microenvironment plays an important role in the formation of life values and interests of a person; -uncertainty of place of residence or permanent residence (the possibility of committing a crime is different for women living in urban and rural areas); - according to the sign of nationality (specific differences in the crime rate of women living in European and Islamic countries)¹³.

It is appropriate to study the subjective and objective reasons and conditions of women's recidivism, and it serves to eliminate the identified reasons and conditions¹⁴.

In other words, traces of crimes committed by women may indicate that the criminal belongs to one or another category.

N. Ibragimova is a crime suggested dividing women with a tendency to commit into three types: the first type is "women with deviant behavior", i.e. "deviation from the norm" (deviant lot. deviatio deviation). The second type includes women who commit crimes due to frustration (inability) (lat. frustratio - delusions, failure of plans), and autism of the third type (alienation from society "autism"). The negative characteristics of women offenders in this category are insufficient social control or extremely negative micro expressed opinions that it is formed in environmental conditions¹⁵.

According to M.V.Yeleskin, we can see that recidivist criminals are divided into three types: 1) women whose danger to society increases with each new crime; 2) women whose level of danger remains the same as before (women who pickpocket); 3) those who have suffered degradation, have lost socially useful connections in the family, everyday life and work community¹⁶.

In addition to the opinions of the above scholars, by studying the types of female criminals, it also helps to prevent them from re-offending.

You can find a lot of opinions of scientists who divide such female criminals into types and classify them. In particular, AG Kovalev classified recidivist women according to the degree of criminal infection:

- 1) global - characterized by complete criminal infection (highly dangerous recidivists);
- 2) paricial - characterized by partial criminal infection;

¹¹ Avanesov G.A. Criminology: textbook. 2-e izd., pererab. i dop. M., 1984. 263 p .

¹² Avanesov G.A. Criminology: textbook. 2-e izd., pererab. i dop. M., 1984. 263 p .

¹³Q.R. Abdurasulova, B.E. Zakirov (Chapter II) "Causes and conditions and prevention of women's crime" Tashkent - 2016.

¹⁴ Nasirov I. S. Criminology Description Of Reciditive Crime // Online Scientific Journal Of Education And Development Analysis. - 2022. - S. 364-380.

¹⁵Ibragimova N. Implementation of educational and preventive measures in women's delinquency //Obshchestvo i innovatsii. - 2022. - T. 3. – no. 5/S. - S. 206-211.

¹⁶See : *Eles'kin M.V.* Osobennosti kriminologicheskoy kharakteristiki lichnosti prestupnika, sovershivshogo prestuplenie v ispravitel'nom uchrejenii // Ugolovno-ispolnitelnaya sistema: pravo, ekonomika, upravlenie. 2008. No. 6. 45 p .

3) pre-crime - its representatives have such moral and psychological characteristics that they inevitably lead to the commission of a crime in a certain situation ¹⁷.

A.D. Glotchkin and V.F. Pattila proposed to classify recidivists into the following types according to the criterion of the desire to commit a new crime:

- 1) the most serious - determined by the internal desire for repeated crimes;
- 2) determined by repeated crime under the influence of circumstances or surrounding persons;
- 3) due to the possibility of accidentally participating in the repetition of crimes or the repetition of crimes due to carelessness^{18 19}.

According to V.A. Kazakova, the nature and circumstances of the committed crime, together with all criminological factors, allow to determine the mechanism of criminal behavior of a person, his criminal tendencies, the level of activity in committing a crime, the level of influence of life situations on this person ²⁰.

Agreed with this opinion and emphasized ²¹that these criteria are crucial in classifying and classifying female criminals.

If we agree with the opinions of the above scientists, and give our suggestions on the classification of female convicts in penal colonies, the first one is "not on the road to reform", that is, sentenced to imprisonment for any crime, and the execution of the sentence newcomers to the colony; the second - as a result of preventive interviews (*after at least 3 months*) with convicts "on the road to recovery", this itself is carried out in two stages. The first step is educational interviews with the participation of other prisoners, and the second stage is learning through preventive interviews by staff. The third is "on the road to recovery", considering that the convict has understood the bad consequences of the crime he committed, conscientiously approached work, fulfilled the established norms, followed the rules of the internal order, and has reached the level where he can be a good example to other convicts. it can be described that he will not commit a crime again.

Criteria for determining whether convicts are on the road to recovery have been developed. According to him, now the prisoner must have a conscientious attitude to work, fulfill the established labor norms, consciously develop the skills of independent work, and be interested in education and vocational training. the prisoner's participation in the cultural and educational activities organized in the penal institutions, his initiative, striving to be an example to other prisoners were ²²introduced.

In order to further develop the process of moral education of convicted recidivist women, it is necessary to create a complete typology of them.

In Ye.I. Yelfimova's opinion, the main typological features of the anti - social direction of the person are his: treating a person's personality and his most important advantages with

¹⁷See : Kovalev A.G. Psikhologicheskie osnovy ispravleniya pravonarushitelya. M., 1968. 50 p .

¹⁸ See : Glotchkin A.D., Pirozhkov V.F. Psikhicheskoe sostoyanie cheloveka, lishennogo svobody: lecture / pod ed. K.K. Platonova. M., 1968. 36 p .

¹⁹See : Platonov K.K. System psychology. M., 1972. 89 p .

²⁰Kazakova V.A. Naznachenie i ispolnenie nakazaniya v otnoshenii genschin, osujdennyx k ispravitelnyx rabotam. Diss. nor soisk. three. Step. sugar go science M., 1984. -S. 29.

²¹ Abdurasulova Q. _ R. _ " Women's crime and problems of their prevention " . Study guide / Responsible editor: yu.fd.prof. MHRustamboev. - T.: TDYI publishing house, 2009. - 32 pages.

²² Law No. O'RQ-817 dated 15.02.2023 " On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legal Documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at Reliable Protection of the Rights and Legal Interests of Prisoners " // <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6384468/> (time of application to the electronic database: 04.05.2023.).

negative attention; selfish and private property views; individualist-anarchist attitude to various universally recognized values and social relations; He stated that it was the result of ²³carelessness and irresponsibility towards his duties .

Issues of the typology of criminals have been considered in the scientific works of many domestic scientists ²⁴, but the problem of classification and typology of recidivist women in criminology is far from the final and only solution.

In A.K. Sumenkov's opinion, he ²⁵tried to determine the recidivist actions of women who committed crimes through four types of typology of recidivists, i.e. malicious direction, aggressive direction, socially passive type, mixed type.

In Yu.A. Alferov's research, penitentiary criminology and psychology came to the opinion that there are other classifications based on individual psychological characteristics of prisoners, including moral-pedagogical negligence ²⁶.

We subscribe to an opinion of scientists, because the typologies of psychological trainings developed for the prevention of recidivist crimes have one main goal - to individualize the effect, and as a result, they are aimed at reducing the percentage of women's recidivism in the future.

In the studies of Ch. Lombroso "Criminal and whore woman" crime women who are guilty of committing how many to types separates:

1. Congenital criminal women;
2. Casual criminal women;
3. Passionate criminal women ²⁷.

As part of our research, we have divided the criminal activities of recidivist women into several types depending on the conditions of living conditions of female criminals and the levels of habituation:

- non-returnable;
- aggressive;
- professional;
- dependent;
- depressed;
- mix.

1) irreversible - recidivists' inability and unwillingness to adapt to society, social and moral degradation, lack of specialization and professional skills, narrowing of the scope of interest, weakening of cognitive processes, impoverishment of emotions, affective instability, impulsiveness of actions, when committing crimes with a position in the group tendency to

²³ Elfimova EI Typology of women who committed crimes as a type of forensic classification // Legal concept. - 2012. - no. 2. - S. 263-268.

²⁴ See : *Sakharov A.B.* Lichnost prostitutes and typology prostitutes // Sots. legality 1973. No. 3. 19-24 p .; *Voronin Yu.A.* Typology lichnosti prestupnikov: autoref. dis ... cand. walk science Sverdlovsk, 1974; *Nadiyarnyy A.V.* Psikhologicheskaya charakteristika tipov pravnorushiteley // Voprosy borby s prestupnostyu. 1974. No. 1. 39-44 b ; *Dagel P.S.* Problema tipologii i klassifikatsii lichnosti neostorojnyx prestupnikov // Voprosy borby s prestupnostyu. M., 1978. Vyp. 28. 3-14 p .

²⁵ See : *Sumenkov A.K.* Recidivism of presuppleny i problemy ispolneniya nakazaniya v vide lishenia svobody: autoref. diss. ... candy. walk science Ryazan, 2003. 12 p .

²⁶ See : *Alferov Yu.A.* Penitentsiarnaya sociology i perevospitanie osujdenykh. Domodedovo, 1994. 78-79 p .

²⁷ <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=44209601> (time of database access: 02/13/2023).

inadequate forms of response, theft, robbery, invasion, predominance of malicious purpose of crimes;

2) aggressive - poor adaptation in society and relatively easy integration into the criminal environment, a decrease in the adaptive mechanisms of self-regulation of behavior, inappropriate emotions of anger, the presence of guilt, increased anxiety, emotional vulnerability, committing murder, health predominance of feelings of serious harm to the victim, jealousy of the victim or fear of the victim;

3) professional-biased - stability of biased intentions, unemployment, increased level of education, being intellectual, tactful, persistent, lying and adapting to environmental conditions through the ability to assume a different image, subtle, predominance of reliable and complex actions, fraud, high-level theft, malice motive;

4) dependent - is determined by employment in the field of drug trafficking, because the disease increases, infantilism and emotional instability alternate with conflict, evil, emotional poverty, lack of fear, hysterical personality traits, high emotions, theatricality, falling in love, romanticism, drug addiction, motives - selfish desires, the need to satisfy bad addictions, self-use of drugs, compassion, "kindness", sympathy;

5) in a depressed state - it is manifested in the violation of professional, service, general civil and other legal obligations by recidivists, the selfish interests of a narrow group dominate them, the use of a special type of psychological protection - it is expressed in the concealment of illegal frauds with "interest" . Hiding with "business interests", "duty of service", looking for new opportunities for criminal methods of action, meeting hypertrophied material needs with unusual manifestations of "poor" life, the main motive is personal malice;

6) mixed (intermediate) - reflects aspects of another type.

